

IMPROVING TRAFFIC SAFETY AT ACCIDENT BLACK SPOTS ON MOUNTAIN ROADS

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Abstract. This article examines accident black spots on the D010 automobile road passing through mountainous areas of the Bostanliq district of Tashkent Region. The study analyzes traffic accidents occurring on this road section, identifies the main causes of road traffic accidents, and develops recommendations aimed at reducing their frequency and improving overall traffic safety.

Keywords: Road traffic accidents; accident black spots; horizontal curve radius; traffic flow intensity; traffic signs; IKSp-2M; emergency escape lane.

INTRODUCTION

Road traffic accidents (RTAs) occurring on automobile roads have a negative impact on the safety of the transport system, social stability, and economic development. Especially in mountainous conditions, due to the complexity of the terrain, roads often pass through steep gradients and areas with numerous curves. On such complex road sections, accident black spots occur more frequently, and traffic accidents taking place at these locations may lead to severe consequences. Ensuring traffic safety on mountainous roads is more complex than on flat roads, because roads passing through mountainous areas have steep longitudinal gradients, small design curve radii, limited sight distances, and are more significantly affected by natural climatic factors. Approximately 22% of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of mountainous and foothill regions [1]. Therefore, enhancing traffic safety at accident black spots on mountainous roads is one of the most pressing challenges today.

Accident black spots are sections of the road where traffic accidents occur most frequently, and their formation is influenced by factors such as the technical condition of structures, the geometric parameters of the road, the absence of road signs, driver discipline, and other factors [2].

Table 1

Requirements for Accident Black Spots in Different Countries

Country	Requirement for Accident Black Spots
Germany	A location where at least 5 similar traffic accidents occurred within 1 year on a 300 m road section
United Kingdom	A location where more than 12 traffic accidents occurred within 3 years on a 300 m road section
Portugal	A location where more than 5 traffic accidents occurred within 1 year on a 200 m road section
Netherlands	A location where a total of 10 traffic accidents occurred within 3–5 years, or at least 5 of the same type

Denmark	A location where 4 traffic accidents occurred within 5 years
Spain	A location where 5 injury accidents or 2 fatal accidents occurred within 1 year on a 1 km road section, or 10 injury accidents or 5 fatal accidents occurred within 3 years

For the purpose of studying accident black spots, two locations on the D010 road passing through the mountainous area of Bostanliq district, Tashkent region, were selected (figure 1).

Figure 1. Two accident black spots on the D010 road.

The first accident black spots is located on a curve between kilometers 1 and 2 of the D010 road (Figure 2). In 2024, three traffic accidents occurred at this location: one collision (resulting in one fatality), one rollover, and one impact with a barrier. In the first half of 2025, one traffic accident involving a barrier collision was recorded.

Figure 2. First accident black spots.

The second accident black spots is located on a curve at kilometer 2 + 900 meters of the D010 road (Figure 3). In 2024, five traffic accidents occurred at this location, all involving collisions with barriers, resulting in two fatalities. In the first half of 2025, two traffic accidents were recorded: one collision and one barrier impact, with the latter resulting in one fatality.

Since the accident black spots are located on a mountainous road, trucks that collided with barriers broke through them and rolled down the slope. As a result, the vehicles sustained severe damage, the drivers suffered serious injuries, and in some cases, fatalities were recorded. The D010 road is classified as a Category III road, and the traffic volume in the sections with accident black spots was determined to be 3,325 vehicles per day, which complies with the current regulatory requirements [3].

Figure 3. Second accident black spots.

The geometric dimensions of the road at the first accident black spots do not meet the established requirements. Specifically, near the accident black spots, the lane widths are 3.30 meters on the right side and 2.80 meters on the left side. On the curve at the accident black spots, the lane widths are 4.50 meters on the right side and 4.80 meters on the left side. In the section following the accident black spots, the lane widths are 3.40 meters on both the right and left sides. The pavement friction coefficient at the accident black spots was determined using the IKSp-2M device and was found to be 0.64, which meets the established requirements. One of the main problems at the accident black spots is that the design curve radius is smaller than the specified standard, with a design curve radius of 22 meters. According to the regulatory requirements, the design curve radius of a Category III road passing through mountainous areas should not be less than 100 meters. A smaller design curve radius increases the risk of vehicle rollover and reduces sight distance in curved sections, which, in turn, increases the likelihood of collisions. On Category III roads passing through mountainous areas, the design speed is set at 50 km/h [3]. However, no speed-limiting signs have been installed on this road.

The geometric dimensions of the road at the second accident black spots are also uneven. Near the accident black spots, the lane widths are 3.10 meters on the right side and 4.10 meters on the left side. On the curve at the accident black spots, the lane widths are 4.50 meters on the right side and 6.20 meters on the left side. In the section following the accident black spots, the lane widths are 4.70 meters on the right side and 5.0 meters on the left side. The pavement friction coefficient at the accident black spots was determined using the IKSp-2M device and was found to be 0.60, which meets the established requirements. One of the main problems at this accident black spots is also that the design curve radius is smaller than the specified standard, with a radius of 27 meters. This value is significantly below the regulatory requirements. Additionally, there are no road signs indicating the prescribed speed at this accident black spots. More than 85% of the

traffic accidents at this accident black spots occurred as a result of heavy trucks moving downhill losing braking control and colliding with barriers.

Conclusion:

The results of the study indicate that the main factors contributing to the formation of accident black spots on roads located in mountainous areas are non-compliance of the road's geometric parameters with regulatory requirements—particularly excessively small design curve radii—the absence of speed-limiting road signs, and brake failures of heavy vehicles while descending slopes.

Although the pavement friction coefficient at the accident black spots meets regulatory standards, it was found that the design curve radii of 22–27 meters—significantly below the minimum required 100 meters—pose a serious threat to traffic safety. Since reconstructing the design curve radii in mountainous terrain involves significant financial and technical challenges, installing speed-limiting road signs is an important short-term and effective measure to enhance traffic safety.

In addition, to reduce traffic accidents related to brake failures of heavy trucks descending slopes, the construction of “escape ramps” has been identified as one of the most effective engineering solutions (Figure 3) [4]. When implemented at the second accident black spots, this measure can help prevent severe traffic accidents.

Figure 3. Emergency escape ramp at Qamchiq Pass

In general, enhancing traffic safety at accident black spots on mountainous roads requires a comprehensive approach. This includes bringing the road’s geometric parameters as close as possible to regulatory standards, installing speed-limiting road signs, and implementing engineering structures for emergency situations. Such measures can significantly reduce both the number of traffic accidents and their severe consequences.

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